

Employees' Job Satisfaction and Organizational Performance: A Case of KSRTC

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ABSTRACT

Managing the people in the organization is the crucial task which helps to get the greatest return in terms of productivity. The management of workforce starts with acquiring the required human resource, providing extensive training and development thereby enhancing employability, maintaining the compensatory issues and finally separate the human resource based on the functional specification. One of the factors of production which contributes the greatest return to the organizational growth and development is employees of the organization. Means they play a crucial role in the organization. The Organization has three major objectives of managing the human resource such are, provide Job satisfaction, optimum utilization of available human resources and, to provide employment opportunities. on this context, the present research addresses the job satisfaction of employees in KSRTC Davangere. The study based on primary data which is collected from a structured questionnaire with Likert five-point scale by a random sample of 50 respondents in Davangere.

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KEYWORDS: Job satisfaction, KSRTC employees, determinants, organizational performance

I. INTRODUCTION

Now a day in the modern era the management of human resource takes different deviations with its task by the convergence of human resource planning as talent management, wage administration as total reward management, move from commodity concept to human asset or human capital management etc. Today the success of individuals' desires and organization desires are measured by their dynamic nature. Organizations have abundance the traditional thinking of what work is and how people should work. Employment now means more than having a job. It is not just something an individual does, but a combination of shared responsibilities and duties between the organization and the individual (**Zorlu Senyuçel**). Human resource management is a management function that helps managers' recruit, train and develops members of an organization. Obviously, HRM is concerned with the people's dimensions in the organization. The role of the Human Resource Department had changed dramatically over the past 30years and will become increasingly more strategic in nature in the future. The emerging trends in human resource Department are Talent Management, Absconding employees, Balanced Scorecard, outsourcing, six sigma. (**Dr. M. Janarthanan 2015**). When people describe employee attitudes or perception, they usually mean job satisfaction, which

describes a positive feeling about their job, resulting from an evaluation of its performance-based characteristics. A person with a high level of job satisfaction definitely holds a positive feeling about his or her job, while a person with a very low-level satisfaction holds negative feelings. The organizational performance and job satisfaction of employees, both are dependent variables which help in getting mutual benefits by both organization as well as employees. The enhancement of productivity of an individual employee is not confined with only economic incentives, why because it influenced by psychological and social dynamics. The present study attempts to analyze employees' job satisfaction in Karnataka Road Transport Corporation in Davangere.

II. Objectives of the Study

- To study the job satisfaction of employees in KSRTC.
- To analyze the factors influence on employees job satisfaction.

III. Research Methodology

Research methodology is a science of studying how research is to be carried out essentially, the procedures by which research go about their work of describing, explaining and

predicting phenomena are called research methodology. It is also defined as the studying of methods by which knowledge is gained. The methodology can be selected as a primary element in any type of research methodology is the method of use to collect information related to the research study. Good research is purely based on data collection.

Method of data collection:

The data is collected in this project is prepared through by meeting the respondents of KSRTC employees There are two types of data. They are:

Primary Data:

Primary data is the first-hand data, the primary data can be collected through survey, interviews. The information collected directly from the primary source. In this paper, the primary data is collected from giving a structured questionnaire to the 50 respondents. The selection of the respondent is based on simple random sampling. In this survey, LIKERT scale technique was used for the questions like strongly agree, agree, disagree and strongly disagree question and also this technique used framing yes or no questions.

Likert Scale:

This method of standardized survey was developed by Likert in 1932 and is widely used even today. In this, as stated earlier, an individual is asked to indicate agreement or disagreement with job factors. The individual is also required to state how strongly he or she agree or disagree with a statement. This is normally done on a 5-point scale, though it is possible to use a 7-point scale also. The normal practice is to incorporate the various statements in a questionnaire. The subject is asked to respond to these statements, indicating the extent of his or her agreement or disagreement.

Secondary data:

Secondary data is second-hand data. The data is already collected by the other persons for another purpose. The secondary data is already existing data. The secondary data is collected from. Reference books Journals Research paper Websites.

IV. Problematization

Employees play an important role in any organizations or departments. So their satisfaction is a very essential one. The employees are the main strength of the Department there arises a need to study the job satisfaction of the employees. The present study has been undertaken to find out the job satisfaction of among KSRTC employees.

V. Need for the study

Employees face many problems due to the culture, technology, work pressure, poor working environment, and etc leads to job dissatisfaction. Thus the organization/employers must focus on the job satisfaction of employees. Working for them to retain the productive and potential workforce and attract the new potential workforce and attract new potential employees. Quality of work life is reflected in the efficiency and effectiveness of an organization both at the micro level and macro level.

VI. Scope and limitations of the study

- This study is essentially a micro level study restricted to KSRTC Davangere.
- There is a time limitation for the study.

- The sample size of the respondents is limited with fifty employees.
- Respondent is not ready to give the information because of fear.

VII. Data Analysis and Interpretation

Table-1 Demographic profile of KSRTC employees					
Gender	Fq	(%)	Marital status	Fq	(%)
Male	39	78	Married	38	76
Female	11	22	Unmarried	12	24
Total	50	100	Total	50	100
Education	Fq	(%)	Age	Fq	(%)
SSLC	08	16	20-25	06	12
PUC	25	50	26-30	12	24
Degree	14	28	31-35	17	34
Others	03	06	36 & above	15	30
Total	20	100	Total	50	100

Source: Field survey

Demographics of KSTRC employees:

The gender status of employees is categorized with 78% of the respondents are male employees and 22% of the respondents are female employees. The KSRTC provides more employment opportunity to the male employees rather than the female employees. The age structure of employees with 34% of the respondent is from the age of 31 to 35 years, 30% of the respondent is 36 and above, 24% of the respondent is 26 to 30 years and remaining 12% of the respondent is from the age group of 20 to 25 years. Half of the KSRTC employees' educational qualification is only PUC, 28% of the respondent are Degree holders, 16% of the respondent qualification is only SSLC and the 6% of the respondent is ITI or any other and 76% of the respondents are married and 24% of respondents are unmarried.

Table-2 Frequency analysis based on the satisfied or not

S. No.	Particulars	Yes (%)	No (%)	Total
1	Salary	52	48	100%
2	Work life balance	72	28	100%
3	Relationship with work	94	06	100%
4	Awards	44	56	100%
5	Requires any training	58	42	100%

Source: Field survey.

Employees' satisfaction:

The KSRTC employees' satisfaction towards their job and the organization with Salary, Fifty-two percent of the respondents they are satisfied with the salary offered by the KSRTC, and forty-eight percent they are not satisfied with salary. The Work-life balance of Seventy-two percent employees is good and remaining twenty-eight percent of the respondent says that they are not balancing their personal life. Thirdly relationship with workers is most important aspect job environment, so ninety-four percent of the respondents say that there is a good relationship with each employee and six percent of the respondents say co-ordination with the other workers is not good. Fourthly awards forty-four percent of the respondents give a positive response about awards and fifty-six percent of the respondent not satisfied with awards to the workers. KSRTC department offers the awards only to the drivers but not to the other employees. If the KSRTC department offers the awards to every employee according to the job it helps to

improve positivity. And lastly, the requirement of training, remaining they are experienced. fifty-eight percent of the respondents requires training

Table-2 Employees response towards KSRTC Davangere						
S. No.	Particulars	S.A%	A%	D.A%	S.D.A%	Total
1	Working hours	18	66	14	02	100%
2	Lunch break, rest and leaves	18	62	18	02	100%
3	Management	08	72	18	02	100%
4	Recognition of work	14	46	36	04	100%
5	Dissemination of Information	16	40	42	02	100%
6	Assets treatment	20	66	10	04	100%
7	Proud to work for KSRTC	42	52	06	00	100%
8	Rules and Regulations	30	60	08	02	100%

Source-Field survey S.A -Strongly Agree A-Agree D.A-Disagree S.D.A-Strongly Disagree

KSRTC and HR functionalism:

- **Working hours:** 18% percent of the respondent strongly agrees, 66% percent of the respondent only agrees, 14% of the respondent disagree and only 2% of the respondent strongly disagree with the working hours of the KSRTC.
- **Lunch break, rest break and leaves:** 18% of the respondents strongly agree with the all these facilities, 62% of the respondent agrees with the facilities 18% of the respondent disagrees with these facilities and only 2% of the respondents not agree with all these facilities given by KSRTC.
- **Management:** Eight percent of the respondent says that they strongly agree, seventy-two percent agrees, eighteen percent of the respondent says disagree, and only two percent of the respondent strongly disagree with the management of the KSRTC.
- **Work recognition:** Fourteen percent of the respondent tells that they strongly agree, forty-six percent of the respondents they agree, eighteen percent of the respondent say that they disagree and only four percent of the respondent strongly disagrees with word recognition.
- **Dissemination of Information:** Only eight percent of the KSRTC employees' strongly agree with the dissemination of information by top-level management; forty percent of the respondent, they agree with this. Forty-two percent of the respondent says that they do not agree with the Dissemination role in KSRTC.
- **Employees are the assets:** when we see the 6th aspects in the table it clears that twenty percent of the respondent say they strongly agree, sixty-six percent of the respondents are agreed with the department treat them as an asset to the KSRTC department, remaining they disagree.
- **Proud to work in KSRTC:** the seventh aspects in the table says forty-two percent of the respondents are strongly agreed to proud to be work with the KSRTC department, fifty-two percent of the respondent say they agree to say proudly to work in the department, remaining they disagree.
- **Rules and Regulations:** last but not listed in the table are rules and regulations, so thirty percent of the respondents say that they strongly agree with the rules and regulation of the KSRTC, sixty percent of the respondents say they agree with the rules and regulation and remaining they are disagree.

VIII. Major Findings of the study

- **Education:** The educational background of the KSRTC employees, they are completed PUC and some of them are completed a degree and other qualification. Who completed the PUC they work as a driver, conductor and mechanics, and rest of the workers in higher positions.
- **Satisfaction:** by observing the employees' response most of the respondents are not fully satisfied with work due to the problems like break time, management pressure and more important issues between conductor and passenger, a conductor is liable to pay the penalty.
- **Management:** management of the KSRTC is somewhat good means, by observing the response it is cleared that management of the KSRTC doesn't give any chance to the employees in decision making.

Awards and acknowledgment:

KSRTC give the awards only to the drivers who do not make any accident in their lifetime work and rest of the employees feel bad because everyone does the same job, but the award given to the driver is not fair.

IX. Suggestions:

- **Change in award system:** Main suggestion to the KSRTC is to award the workers according to their experience and their work in the organization and also recognize their work and motivate the other employees to work ineffectively. By observing the recognition other employees can do the job effectively and efficiently.
- **Participative management:** The KSRTC top-level management must use the advice from the employees on the time of taking any decision regarding the changes in the division and management consider the employees are the most impotent asset to the KSRTC.
- **Change in rest period:** Must increase the lunch break time only 5 minutes is not in half to lunch on the time of travelling from one place to another place for long distance and also give the leaves for the strong reason without asking the strong proof for sanctioning the leaves to the workers.
- **Training for new entrants:** On the time of hiring the new employees KSRTC must give the proper training to each new fresher to avoid the accident and also give the training to the mechanics and also drivers.

Conclusion

So finality of the study is not confined only with employee's job satisfaction towards KSRTC. The organizational performance and job satisfaction of employees, both are dependent variables which help in getting mutual benefits by

both organizations as well as employees. The enhancement of productivity of an individual employee is not confined with only economic incentives, why because it influenced by psychological and social dynamics. By observing demographics, employees response about elements of satisfaction and HR practices in KSRTC it is clear that there is a need to change in the system of managing the human resource in the organization. Such changes like award system, work recognition, rest period, participative management, and training for new employees. Today in emerging arena employees are the assets of the organization, especially in KSRTC without employees there is nothing, means all the work will be done only through the employees. Currently, in the KSRTC, more than 20,000 employees are working. The government needs to intervene and consider the employees' response and requirements for both organizational and employees with interest of the general public.

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